

Supporting Information

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2 **Liquid-solid contact electrification when water droplets hit living plant** 3 **leaves**

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12 **Supplementary Figure 1. Droplet maximum expansion area and perimeter extracted from**
 13 **high-speed videos.** Red bars show results for droplets interacting with *A. macrorrhiza* leaves
 14 while pink bars refer to tests *C. antiquorum* leaves. The first group of bars shows the area (in
 15 cm²) when the droplet, after impact, reaches its maximum expansion. The second group
 16 summarizes the perimeter of the droplet (in cm) at maximum spread. Standard deviations from
 17 10 samples per bar are given. Interestingly, this data does not vary significantly between the two
 18 species despite their different wetting properties. Thus, the expansion areas are not significantly
 19 affected by the leaf wetting properties, but rather by the droplet kinetics and the liquid
 20 deformation due to the impact. The microscopic contact area driven by the microstructure and
 21 the surface composition may still be different for both species, as expected from their wetting
 22 properties. However, the overall spread of the droplet is important for electrostatic induction in
 23 which the droplet forms a plate of a charged capacitor.

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26 **Supplementary Figure 2. Snapshot of the experimental setup.** The image shows the
27 instrumentation and setup of a typical experiment.

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32 **Supplementary Figure 3. Relationship between the inner diameter of the syringe and the**
33 **drop volume (mL).** Varying the diameter allows controlling the droplet volume. Each box chart
34 summarizes the statistics of the experiments over 50 droplets. For most experiments reported in
35 this article, a syringe with an inner diameter of 1.6 mm was then used.

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40 **Supplementary Figure 4. Time-resolved electrical signals showing signal shape in high**
 41 **resolution.** Current (a.), charge (b.) and voltage (c.) signals generated by a single droplet
 42 impact on the two model species, *A. macrorrhiza* and *C. antiquorum*.

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45 **Supplementary Figure 5. Electrical signals as function of droplet number contacting *C.***
 46 ***antiquorum* (first column) and *A. macrorrhiza* (second column) leaves. a) current, b)**
 47 **charge, and c) voltage signals, respectively recorded in pristine leaves. Each datapoint**
 48 **represents mean and standard deviation of 50 droplets.**

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50 **Supplementary Figure 6. Reproducibility of signal generation by multiple droplets and on**
 51 **different leaves.** a) and b) show signals obtained from different leaves of *A. macrorrhiza* and *C.*
 52 *antiquorum*, respectively using leaves from the same and different plants during dropping of
 53 about 20 droplets of DI water in sequence. Each experiment was repeated three times. In the
 54 graphs, one of the three replicates is shown representatively as the three replicates of the same
 55 leaf did not vary significantly. The two species produce reproducible signals, both in shape and
 56 magnitude. Moreover, the signals vary only slightly in magnitude when comparing data from

57 different leaves of the same species. The significant difference in the magnitude and polarity
58 comparing *A. macrorrhiza* and *C. antiquorum* is clearly reproduced in all cases.

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61 **Supplementary Figure 7. Impedance spectroscopy of the plant tissue.** a) Plots showing the
62 impedance between stem and different points of the leaf, in *A. macrorrhiza* (left) and *C.*
63 *antiquorum* (right). b) Impedance between stem and lamina of *C. antiquorum* of leaf before and
64 after melting the waxes. c) Impedance between stem and lamina of *C. antiquorum* of leaf before
65 and after removing the waxes through a CHCl_3 treatment.

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67 **Supplementary Figure S8. Summary of the electric signals recorded on *A. macrorrhiza***
 68 **and *C. antiquorum* with DI water and positively and negatively pre-charged DI water. The**

69 current a), charge b), and voltage c) are given. The left column shows the charge of the first
70 droplet passing through the faraday cup before landing on the leaf. The middle column shows
71 signals of the droplet in contact with *A. macrorrhiza*, while the right column shows the signals
72 relative to *C. antiquorum*, respectively. In each block, the first row shows the results when no
73 precharge is applied to the water droplet; while positive precharge and negative precharge
74 conditions correspond to the second and third row, respectively.

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78 **Supplementary Figure 9. The electric signals recorded on *A. macrorrhiza* and *C.***
 79 ***antiquorum* using a 1M NaCl solution, uncharged and with positive/negative precharge.**

80 The current a), charge b), and voltage c) are given. The left and right columns report the signals
 81 for *A. macrorrhiza* and *C. antiquorum*, respectively. In each block, the first, second and third row
 82 shows samples without precharge, with with positive precharge, and with negative precharge of
 83 the droplets, respectively.

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 86 **Supplementary Figure 10. Influence of ion concentration on the current signals'**
 87 **amplitude.** The boxplot summarizes data from 20 droplets each. Blue boxes refer to data
 88 obtained with deionized water while orange boxes to a solution 1M NaCl.

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C. antiquorum - pristine

C. antiquorum - heat treated

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92 **Supplementary Figure 11. Digital micrographs of the leaf surface.** The images show the

93 different appearance of a *C. antiquorum* leaf before and after heat treatment.

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96 **Supplementary Figure 12. FTIR spectroscopy of the leaves.** a) Comparison of *C. antiquorum*
 97 in its pristine state, as well as 10 and 180 minutes after wax removal, respectively. b) FTIR
 98 spectra of *A. macrorrhiza* and *C. antiquorum* in their dry state (top panel), and pristine, fresh
 99 state (bottom panel). The yellow bars highlight the bands that can be attributed to the waxes in

100 line with Ref. 36. The related bands diminish after wax removal on *C. antiquorum*. Moreover,
101 the comparison between *A. macrorrhiza* and *C. antiquorum* shows different intensities, which are
102 in line with the different wax composition and distribution on both species. This is also confirmed
103 by the SEM images in Fig. 1.

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106 **Supplementary Figure 13. Effect of wax treatment on triboelectric signals.** Current, charge,
107 and voltage signals recorded for *C. antiquorum* of pristine leaves (left column), after changing

108 the nanostructure of the epicuticular waxes by melting (center column) and after wax removal by
109 chloroform (right column). Experiments were performed with DI water.

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117 **Supplementary Figure 14. Surface structure and wetting properties of *N. oleander*, *H.***
118 ***helix*, *N. nucifera* and *T. majus* leaves. a) and b) SEM images which detail the micro- and**
119 **nanoscopic features of the leaves' surfaces. c) Water contact angle of the four leaf species;**
120 **standard deviation from 5 measurements is given.. The insets show the droplet on the**
121 **corresponding leaf surface.**

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123 **Supplementary Figure 15. Electric signals due to liquid-solid contact electrification of**

124 **artificial materials.** a) Boxplot comparing the current signals produced by DI water droplets

125 impinging on PET, silicone rubber, PTFE and FEP. b) Structure of the four artificial systems for

126 measuring liquid-solid contact electrification on the top surface. c) Current, charge and voltage

127 amplitudes as function of number of droplets (data points and error bars represent mean and

128 standard deviation of 50 droplets each).

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131 **Supplementary Table 1.** List of hypothesized biological functions correlated to the
 132 superhydrophobic leaf properties previously described in the literature.

Reference	Hypothesized biological function/benefit								
41	Shedding water to avoid mechanical instability	Capturing of insects (carnivorous plants)	Avoiding contaminations by water-born fungi/pathogens	Buoyancy	Thermal isolation	Drag reduction	Sensory function	Camouflage	Avoiding formation of water layers to improve photosynthesis
40	Self-cleaning	Water repellency							
39	Avoiding formation of biofilms	Avoiding formation of water layers to improve photosynthesis							
2	Avoiding contaminations by water-born fungi/pathogens	Reflection of sunlight by epicuticular waxes	A dense layer of epicuticular waxes help contrast stress from sand, detritus & salt	Dust particles increase surface temperature considerably.	Avoiding formation of water layers to improve photosynthesis				

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